

Temperature evolution of exchange-driven magnetism of non-conducting glass-like carbon

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Abstract

Magnetic properties of glass-like carbon (GLC) obtained by pyrolysis of furfuryl alcohol at 600° are studied by continuous wave electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) in the temperature range of 4.3–300 K. The pulsed EPR is used for measuring the spin relaxation times and the spin multiplicity of the observed paramagnetic centers. Nutation experiments detect only doublet spin states in our samples. Complex non-Curie temperature dependences of paramagnetic susceptibility for samples prepared under different conditions (degassing, annealing and storage time) are observed. The strong influence of preparation conditions is results from nanoporosity detected by small-angle X-ray scattering. The wide-angle X-ray scattering reveals that average basic units of GLC600 consist of stacks of three graphene-like strongly defected planes. It is shown that the temperature dependences of the EPR parameters are caused by temperature changes in the number of paramagnetic centers and are explained by the disintegration of exchange-coupled pairs. These dependences for samples with different degrees of degassing demonstrate that the exchange coupling is destroyed by adsorbed gases. Although the probabilities of triplet and singlet ground states of these pairs are the same, the

triplet states are not detected in either continuous wave or nutation EPR experiments, perhaps due to the large fine splitting.

1. Introduction

The properties of non-graphitizing carbons that are obtained by pyrolysis of various organic materials and known as glass-like carbons (GLCs) have been intensively studied using various methods for over 50 years [1–5]. Research interest was driven by the high application potential of these materials resulting from high thermal and electrical conductivity accompanied by high chemical resistance and excellent mechanical strength. In addition, it is possible to tailor properties of GLCs to specific needs through high-temperature treatment (HTT), which affects the mechanisms of chemical transformations in the pyrolysis process. Magnetic properties of these materials have not yet been sufficiently studied. Due to the high spin concentration ($10^{18} - 10^{20}$ spin/gram), GLCs should be of interest to the electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) community. Instead, only a few papers focusing on the effect of HTT on EPR parameters and spin concentration have been published since 1970 [6–11]. According to these papers, the magnetic moments observed by EPR arise from dangling bonds due to any unsatisfied valence on an immobilized atom or molecule. The temperature dependence of the EPR signal parameters can provide important information on the nature of paramagnetic centers (PCs). However, such dependence has been presented only in one paper [7], in the limited temperature range of 100–300 K, and was used to determine whether localized or delocalized magnetic moments predominate in the samples.

Recently, our research group has shown that unpaired electrons in a doublet state coexist in GLC with the exchange-coupled electrons in the thermally excited triplet states [12]. The presence of triplet states was revealed by Rabi oscillations (transient nutations) in the pulsed EPR taking into account peculiarities in these oscillations for fast-relaxing electron spins [13]. The sample studied in ref. [12] was obtained by HTT at 850 °C and it was electrically conducting [14].

Coexistence of localized paramagnetic states and conduction electrons with similar values of g -factor results in exchange interactions between these two reservoirs of magnetic moments [15,16] which strongly complicates data analysis. It is known that Pauli paramagnetism is suppressed in disordered or nanocrystalline materials in which the electrons undergo Anderson [16,17] or Mott [18–20] localization. The localization causes the magnetic moments of these electrons to exhibit Curie paramagnetism. Such conditions can be realized in GLCs synthesized at HTT below 730 °C [17]. In particular, GLCs obtained by low-temperature pyrolysis of furfuryl alcohol (FA) at 600 °C are characterized by low temperature-activated electrical conductivity [14,18,19]. Moreover, a very narrow pore size distribution is characteristic for

these materials [20]. The nanopores act as molecular sieves, making them appealing for various applications, including catalysis and gas separation [21,22]. On the other hand, nanopores can significantly affect the magnetic properties of these materials due to interactions with trapped atmospheric gases and water.

In the present paper, we report continuous wave and pulsed EPR studies of GLC600 pyrolyzed at relatively low temperature (600 °C) to prevent DC conductivity through percolation and, consequently, the formation of the conduction band. Narrow EPR lines in this material and the absence of Pauli paramagnetism allowed us to reveal a multi-step temperature-induced decrease in the PC number under temperature lowering in the range of 4.3–300 K. To determine intrinsic properties of the observed PCs, we study the storage-time-induced variability of EPR spectra parameters as well as the influence of adsorbed atmospheric gases. We exploit Rabi oscillations in the pulsed EPR to determine a spin multiplicity of the observed PCs. The EPR results are analyzed taking into account structural models of GC600 based on X-ray scattering data.

2. Materials and methods

The glass-like carbon (GLC600) used in our studies was prepared by pyrolysis of furfuryl alcohol (FA). FA was first polymerized by addition of 5 % (v/v) 0.1 M p-toluenesulfonic acid dissolved in ethanol and then hardened at 120 °C for 2 h. Subsequently, the obtained FA polymer was pyrolyzed in argon gas flow. The heating rate during the pyrolysis was 10 °C/h from 20 °C to 200 °C and 5 °C/h from 200 °C to 600 °C. Once this temperature was reached, it was held constant for two hours and then the sample was cooled down naturally in Ar flow [23]. The obtained bulk GLC was ground into powder in a steel mill in the air. The atomic structure and related-properties of GCL600 were characterized previously by other methods [23–25]. X-ray fluorescence spectroscopy (XRF) results revealed that the sample is composed of 94 at. % of carbon, about 6 at. % of oxygen and less than 0.1 at. % of other elements [23]. Although the XRF method does not precisely determine the amount of light elements, the results obtained here are very similar to the elemental composition determined by the flask combustion method for GLC pyrolyzed at 600 °C from FA and furan resins [26]. In [26], 2 wt. % of H was detected. This could be due to slightly different preparation conditions: the heating rate was significantly higher, and this GLC was not held up at the maximum temperature for a time, but was immediately cooled. Other studies of GLC obtained from phenolic resin have shown that the

mass loss during thermal decomposition is total at 600 °C, and above this temperature, no hydrogen release occurs in either an oxidizing or an inert atmosphere [27]. The results of recent molecular dynamics simulations of the GLC formation during furan resin pyrolysis [36] are consistent with the results of elemental composition characterized by the experimental techniques here and in other reports [26,27], because they show only residual amount of H and O atoms (below 2 at. %) in GLCs heated above 500 °C. Taking into account the above-mentioned results, we may assume that the amount of non-carbon elements such as O and H in the GLC600 sample is negligible.

High-resolution transmission electron microscopy (HRTEM) images [23] showed that the structure of GLC600 is homogenous and consists of tangled and cross-linked carbon nano-sized layers. However, in some spots, stacks of more or less parallel graphene-like layers could be discerned. A more detailed characterization of the average atomic structure of this GLC was provided by the wide-angle X-ray scattering (diffraction) method (WAXS). Details of the WAXS measurements, data treatment and modeling can be found in [24,25].

Porosity of GLC600 was studied using the small-angle X-ray scattering (SAXS) technique. SAXS data were collected on the 9-ID-C beamline at the Advanced Photon Source, Argonne National Laboratory, USA. Detailed information about SAXS measurements and data processing can be found in [28–32].

Samples for EPR studies were prepared from GLC600 powder diluted 1:40 by weight with spectrally pure MgO powder. This enables preparation of samples containing less than 0.1 mg of GLC600, i.e. small enough to avoid distortions of EPR spectra due to the vacuum Rabi splitting [12,33,34]. Since GLC600 was grinded and stored in air, an adsorption of paramagnetic molecular oxygen increased relaxation rates of intrinsic PCs resulting in broadening of the EPR line. Therefore, for the EPR studies of the intrinsic properties of GLC600, the EPR samples should have been thoroughly degassed before measurements. For this purpose, the powder mixture was transferred into quartz EPR tubes, evacuated under vacuum for 4 hours and then annealed at 200 °C. Vacuum pressures and annealing times are presented in Table 1. Finally, quartz tubes were sealed under vacuum (see Table 1).

Table 1. GLC600 sample preparation conditions.

	Pressure [mBar]	Annealing time at 200 °C [minutes]
sample 1	0.66	5
sample 2	3.2×10^{-2}	30
sample 3	1.6×10^{-2}	30

The continuous wave EPR measurements were carried out using an X-band Radiopan spectrometer with a TM110 cylinder cavity. Quality factor Q of a loaded cavity was about 3500. Magnetic field modulation frequency was 100 kHz. Spin concentrations of GLC600 samples were determined by comparing their spectra with the spectrum of CuSO_4 single crystal of the known mass (and thus known spin concentration). The CuSO_4 single crystal was placed on the sample tube. Consequently, both spectra were recorded under the same experimental conditions.

A Bruker ELEXSYS E580 spectrometer was used for pulse experiments. The temperature control was realized using a thermostated flow of nitrogen vapors in a CF935 Oxford Cryostat. A Bruker dielectric MD5 cavity was set at a low Q -value to dump the ringing and to shorten the dead time (100 ns ca) before to acquire an artifact-free signal. The transient nutation experiments on the GC600 stored sample 2 were performed measuring a free induction decay (FID) amplitude with a delay (dead time) of 100-120 ns after the microwave (MW) excitation pulse as a function of the pulse length at a fixed attenuation of the microwaves [13]. Calibration of the amplitude B_1 of MW field was carried out using as a reference a γ -irradiated quartz sample (E' centers, $S = 1/2$) [35]. Because of the inhomogeneous broadening of the E' center line, the nutations were observed using a 2-pulse echo experiment and a 2-step phase cycle to cancel FID contributions. Two sets of measurements were conducted using $\pi/2$ pulses of 16 or 40 ns. Measurements on the reference and GLC600 samples were carried out at the same Q -value.

3. Results

3.1. Structural characterization

The diffraction pattern of a non-crystalline material, such as GLC600, is often analyzed in the reciprocal scale and real space representations in the form of the total structure factor

$S(q)$ and the atomic pair distribution function $PDF(r)$, respectively. $S(q)$ is related to the coherent part of the total diffracted intensity of the material (Bragg peaks due to long range order and diffuse scattering due to short-range order), and $PDF(r)$ is simply the Fourier transform of $S(q)$ defined in the scattering vector q space to the real space of distances r . $PDF(r)$ measures the probability of finding an atom at a distance r from a reference atom and so describes the atomic arrangement and is especially sensitive to the short-range order. In turn, $S(q)$ gives more details on the longer-range structural correlations. Therefore, fitting structural models to both, $S(q)$ and $PDF(r)$, may provide more accurate structure refinement. Analysis of the total structure factor and atomic pair distribution function obtained from the WAXS measurements indicated that the structure of GLC600 can be described as consisting of defective aromatic-carbon domains with a very limited range (up to only about 1.2 nm) of structural correlations and a limited stacking order typical for turbostratic carbon. The performed structural modelling showed that the average basic building blocks of GLC600 are stacks of 3 graphene-like planes of 1.6 nm \times 0.9 nm in size, exhibiting a paracrystalline distortion of the carbon network [24]. The physical implementation of the paracrystalline perturbation can be associated with the presence of different types of topological defects, such as vacancies and Stone-Wales defects. Therefore, in order to verify the correctness of structural models containing such topological defects, molecular dynamics simulations were performed according to the methodology described in [25]. In these models, only C atoms were taken into account since, as mentioned above, non-carbon elements in GLC obtained by pyrolysis of FA resins at 600 °C are residual.

Figures 1 a, b and c present the comparison between the experimental structure factor $S(q)$ of GLC and the $S(q)$ calculated using the following optimized models: a domain consisting of three stacking graphene planes of 1.6 nm \times 0.9 nm in size (Figure 1g), a domain of the same size with three monovacancy (MV) defects (Figure 1h), and a domain of the same size with three Stone-Wales (SW) defects (Figure 1i). The defects were randomly located in the graphene planes, and their number was selected in such a way as to ensure the best fit to the experimental diffraction data. Figures 1d, e and f depict a comparison of the experimental atomic pair distribution function $PDF(r)$ for GLC600 and the $PDF(r)$ functions calculated using the above-mentioned models (Figures 1g, h and i). The confrontation of the model-based $S(q)$ and $PDF(r)$ with the experimental data indicates that the basic graphene-like building blocks of GLC600 contain topological defects. Models without such defects do not fit the experimental diffraction data. It is difficult to distinguish what type of defects – SW or MV

defects – are more preferable in this material, since in this case they produce a similar graphene-network distortion. The presence of both types of defects is expected in the real GLC600 structure. Figures 1 g, h and i present visualizations of these atomic models. One can see that the presence of MV and SW defects introduces distortion, rippling and curvature of graphene planes. What is more, cross-links between the stacking planes are formed in which non-planar sp^2 carbon bonds participate.

Figure 1. Comparison of different models of GLC600 structure. (a-c) Experimental structure factors and (d-f) atomic pair distribution functions obtained from wide-angle X-ray diffraction studies of the total scattering intensity. The structure factors and the atomic pair distribution functions were calculated for the models without topological defects (black lines), with monovacancy defects (blue lines) and with Stone-Wales defects (green lines). (g-i) Visualization of the models used for calculations: without topological defects (g), with monovacancy defects (h), and with Stone-Wales defects (i).

The basic structural units of GLC600 in the visualizations shown in Figures 1 are in agreement with the picture of the atomic structure revealed by transmission electron microscopy [23]. Figure 2 shows the SAXS data for GLC600, which provide information on its microstructure. Generally, the power law behavior ($I = Aq^{-Exp}$) of the scattering intensity I in the low q range can be ascribed to the surface area of powder grains. The slope constant $Exp = 3.8$ corresponds to the so-called Porod's law ($I = Aq^{-4}$) of scattering by sharp interfaces and the constant A is proportional to the surface area. However, deviations from Porod's law, resulting in $Exp < 4$, are often observed for disordered carbon materials exhibiting some roughness (fractals) in the mesoscopic range [36]. Here, GLC600 is characterized by $Exp =$

3.8, indicating a fractal character of the surface. Moreover, the characteristic inflection at high q -values referred to as the “Guiner knee” indicates the existence of nanopores in disordered carbon materials [36]. The average radius of pores r_p can be calculated from $r_p = \sqrt{5/3} R_g$, if the shape of the pores is assumed to be nearly spherical and R_g is the radius of gyration. To obtain information on the size distribution of scattering objects, in this case nanopores contributing to the Guiner region, the data were fitted using a regularization method and assuming a model of spherical, not-interacting, and diluted scatterers. The fit and the obtained size distribution are shown in Figure 2. The calculated value of R_g is 5 Å (0.5 nm) and the mean diameter is 9 Å (0.9 nm). This corresponds to size of small voids between the curved graphene layers observed in TEM images in [23] and in Figure S2.

Figure 2. Porosity of GC600. SAXS curve is presented by the black line. The dotted green and red lines are the best fits to the experimental data using the power law $I = 4.6 \times 10^{-6} q^{-3.8}$ at low q -values and the regularization method at high q -values in the Guiner region, respectively. The obtained size distribution of the scattering nanopores is shown by the red histogram.

3.2. Magnetic properties. Continuous wave EPR

The number of PCs in each sample was determined using a $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ single crystal as a standard. The spin concentration values determined for the studied fresh and stored samples are presented in Table 2.

Table 2. Spin concentration of three differently prepared GLC600 samples determined assuming that all centers have $S = 1/2$.

	sample 1 [Spin/g]	sample 2 [Spin/g]	sample 3 [Spin/g]
Fresh	1×10^{20}	1.1×10^{20}	5.0×10^{19}
Stored	5.8×10^{19} After 11 months	8.1×10^{19} After 1 month	5.0×10^{19} After 3 month
Reheated	7.2×10^{19}		

The EPR spectra of all GLC600 samples prepared by the vacuum annealing method consist of a single Lorentzian line, the width ΔB_{pp} of which depends on the amount of adsorbed atmospheric gases. Results of studies of three samples of GLC600 as a function of temperature, degree of degassing and storage time are shown in Figure 3. In order to compare these results, the EPR signal intensity, proportional to the paramagnetic susceptibility χ_{EPR} , was normalized by dividing it by the sample mass.

Figure 3. Temperature dependences of EPR susceptibility (a), (b), (c) and linewidth ΔB_{pp} (d), (e), (f) for three differently prepared GLC600 samples (see Materials and Methods). (a) and (d) The sample 1. (b) and (e) The sample 2. The inset in (b) shows the observed EPR spectrum for the fresh sample 2 (the grey circles) and its fit (the black line) using a Lorentzian line with $\Delta B_{pp} = 0.032$ mT. (c) and (f) The sample 3. Closed and opened

symbols are used for the fresh and stored samples, respectively. Green and red lines show Curie-type temperature dependences for the fresh and stored samples, respectively. The inset demonstrates that χ_{EPR} of the sample **3** does not depend on the storage time.

Figure 3a shows the temperature dependence of paramagnetic susceptibility ($\chi_{EPR}(T)$) for the freshly prepared sample **1**, degassed at low vacuum and shortly (about 5 minutes) annealed at 200 °C. The observed χ_{EPR} decreases with temperature lowering from room temperature (RT) to 270 K. In the temperature range from 260 K to 100 K, $\chi_{EPR}(T)$ follows the Curie law, as it can be expected for the localized non-interacting or weakly interacting paramagnetic centers. However, at lower temperatures the $\chi_{EPR}(T)$ dependence is significantly weaker than the Curie one and at the lowest temperatures the decrease in χ_{EPR} can be noticed. The EPR linewidth of this sample (Figure 3d) is weakly dependent on temperature and increases with temperature lowering. χ_{EPR} of the sample **1** decreases with time of storage at RT. Another cycle of measurements, performed 11 months later, revealed that the RT intensity of the EPR line (open squares) decreased by half and the $\chi_{EPR}(T)$ dependence was weaker than the Curie law in the whole temperature range. Time-induced changes in the $\chi_{EPR}(T)$ dependence were accompanied by the changes in the linewidth which increases from 0.062 mT to 0.066 mT at RT and from 0.079 to 0.1 mT near liquid He temperature, as it is shown in Figure 3d.

The sample **2** was prepared in a higher vacuum with longer annealing time (Table 1). Results are gathered in Figures 3b and 3e. Clearly, a longer annealing of the sample **2** results in a smaller EPR linewidth, which changes in the range 0.032 - 0.045 mT. The linewidth of this sample is also more stable over time: three-week storage at RT results in a very slight broadening at high temperatures, which becomes significant only at low temperatures where the maximum value of $\Delta B_{pp} = 0.051$ mT. Storage resulted in a decrease in χ_{EPR} values, but the $\chi_{EPR}(T)$ dependences of the fresh and stored sample have a similar character. The RT EPR intensity of the fresh sample was comparable with that of the sample **1**, but the $\chi_{EPR}(T)$ dependence was significantly weaker than the Curie law in the whole temperature range.

The sample **3** was prepared under higher vacuum conditions (Table 1). The results obtained for this sample are shown in Figures 3c and 3f and demonstrate much lower intensity of the EPR line, which, however, appeared to be stable over time (the inset in Figure 3c). The $\chi_{EPR}(T)$ dependences recorded after different times of sample storage were the same within the measurement error; therefore we show only one representative dependence. The EPR line was slightly broader than that recorded for the sample **2**, and changed with temperature in the range 0.035-0.049 mT (Figure 3f), but did not depend on the storage time.

It should be pointed here that the atypical weak temperature dependences of χ_{EPR} and increasing the EPR linewidth with temperature lowering were observed for various types of the amorphous carbon [37–40]. Due to its very low electrical conductivity, GLC600 has another property similar to with amorphous carbon: the Anderson localization of π electrons arising from a large number of defects that disrupt the periodicity of the crystal field potential [41]. The localization is responsible for the absence of Pauli paramagnetism.

3.3. Magnetic properties. Pulsed EPR

Figure 4. Rabi oscillations of GLC600 at room temperature (a) and 80 K (b) for two values of the MW amplitude B_1 . The red lines are the best fits Equation (1) to the experimental data using the measured values of the relaxation times. (c) Oscillation frequencies as a function of the MW amplitude B_1 for GLC600 and the E' centers in quartz

at RT and at 80 K. The blue and green lines are a linear fit to the oscillation frequencies of the E' centers and GLC600, respectively.

In order to further investigate the nature of the paramagnetic centers, transient nutation (Rabi oscillation) experiments were performed using the stored sample **2**. The nutation frequency (the so-called Rabi frequency) is determined by the product of the transition matrix element and the amplitude of MW field, is in principle different for different quantum transitions and is used to directly determine electron spin multiplicities [12,35,42]. FID signals were used to observe Rabi oscillations and for measuring relaxation times. The observed signal is well approximated by a single exponential function with the relaxation time $T_2 = 214 \pm 10$ ns at RT and $T_2 = 202 \pm 10$ ns at 80 K. The measured T_2 value at room temperature is consistent with the value $T_2 = 230 \pm 10$ ns obtained from the continuous wave EPR linewidth. FID-detected inversion recovery experiments, fitted with a single exponential function, yielded the spin-lattice relaxation time $T_1 = 613 \pm 10$ ns at RT and $T_1 = 994 \pm 10$ ns at 80 K.

Figure 4 shows the results of transient nutation experiments for the sample **2** and the E' centers in a γ -irradiated quartz at room temperature and 80 K. The E' centers were used as a reference with an electron spin $S = 1/2$. In our experiments, the Rabi frequency $\omega_1 = \gamma B_1$ (γ is the electron gyromagnetic ratio, B_1 is the MW amplitude) is much higher than the spin relaxation rates. As a result, conditions of the strong-field approximation ($\omega_1 \gg 1/T_2, 1/T_1$) are fulfilled and Rabi oscillations at the on-resonance MW excitation of a two-level system can be described by the following simple formula [13]:

$$v_R = M_0 \sin(\omega_1 t) \exp \left[-\frac{t}{2} \left(\frac{1}{T_2} + \frac{1}{T_1} \right) \right], \quad (1)$$

where M_0 is the equilibrium magnetization. At this approximation, the frequency ω_R of Rabi oscillations does not depend on the spin relaxation rates and is equal to ω_1 for a spin system with $S = 1/2$. Rabi oscillations for the sample **2** at room temperature and 80 K are presented in Figures 2a and 2b, respectively. These oscillations are well fitted with Eq. (1) using the measured values of the relaxation times. Their frequencies are proportional to the MW amplitude B_1 which was determined from the Rabi frequency for the E' centers. The oscillation frequencies obtained for our sample increase linearly with the microwave amplitude B_1 at both room temperature and 80 K, exhibiting similar slopes as the dependence observed for the $S = 1/2$ reference (Figure 4c). This indicates the absence of higher spin states ($S > 1/2$) in our sample. It is known that in multilevel spin systems ($S > 1/2$) higher oscillation frequencies can be observed. In particular, it was found that triplet states ($S = 1$) can exist in GLC [12].

Their oscillation frequency is higher than ω_1 for the spin system with $S = 1/2$. When a zero-field splitting parameter D is much larger than ω_1 , the oscillation frequency is $\omega_R = \omega_1\sqrt{2}$ for triplet states and exceeds ω_1 . In the intermediate case $D \sim \omega_1$, several oscillation frequencies, which differ from $\sqrt{2}\omega_1$ and ω_1 , can be observed. Figure 4c shows that this situation does not occur in our sample.

4. Discussion

When analyzing the obtained results, additional information can be obtained from the temperature dependence of the product $\chi_{EPR}T$. Since GLC pyrolyzed at 600 °C shows only weak hopping conductivity, the contribution of Pauli paramagnetism of conduction electrons is absent and all PCs (with $S = 1/2$) should show temperature-dependent paramagnetism. For the Curie-type dependence $\chi_{EPR}T = C$ should be constant. Since the Curie constant $C = Ng^2\mu_B^2S(S + 1)/3k$ is proportional to the number of spins N in the sample and consequently to the spin concentration defined as $C_S = N/m_{GLC}$ (m_{GLC} is the mass of GLC in the sample), any changes in values of $\chi_{EPR}T$ can be interpreted as being caused by C_S . So, the problem that needs to be solved is the reason for the temperature dependence of C_S . The $C_S(T)$ dependencies are presented in Figures 5a, 5b and 5c.

Figure 5. Temperature dependences of spin concentration C_S for three differently prepared GLC600 samples (see Materials and Methods). (a) The sample 1. (b) The sample 2. (c) The sample 3. Closed and opened symbols are used for the fresh and stored samples, respectively.

The rapid (about 20 %) decrease in C_S observed on cooling the sample 1 from 300 to 270 K (Figure 5a) corresponds to the slight decrease in the EPR signal intensity in the same temperature range (Figure 3a). In the range of 100-270 K the C_S value is nearly constant (within the measurement error), but at lower temperatures its significant decrease (of exponential character) is observed. This decrease cannot be explained by the contribution of Pauli Paramagnetism. 11 months of storage significantly diminishes spin concentration observed at RT. The $C_S(T)$ dependences of the fresh and three-week stored sample 2 (Figure 5b) are similar to each other and show strong slopes with several distinct bends. After storage at RT, the C_S value decreases by almost one third. Results obtained for the sample 1 and the sample 2 suggest that the signal intensity varies with storage time, and, therefore, variation of the spin concentration is a rule for GLC600. However, for the most degassed sample 3 (Figure 5c), the linewidth ΔB_{pp} (Figure 5f) and the RT intensity χ_{EPR} (the inset in Figure 3c), and hence the RT spin concentration C_S do not change over months. Table 2 evidences that the spin concentration in the sample 3 is approximately half of that observed for the fresh sample 1 and sample 2 and lower than that of the sample 1 stored for 11 months. This indicates that processes responsible for the storage-induced decrease in C_S are very fast in the deeply degassed sample 3 and $C_S = 0.5 \times 10^{19}$ spin/g seems to be equilibrium concentration for the stored samples. Apparently, degassing by vacuum annealing at 200 °C removes both the adsorbed atmospheric gasses and products of pyrolysis entrapped in nanopores of GLC600. Therefore, the decrease in the EPR line intensity observed in the stored samples 1 and 2 can be caused by the gradual detachment of adsorbed gas molecules under static vacuum.

In the case of thermally excited PCs, the excitation energy from the nonmagnetic ground state to the magnetic excited state can be determined from the dependence of $\ln(\chi_{EPR}T) \sim \ln(C_S(T))$ on $1/T$. Such dependence obtained for the sample 3 is presented in Figure 6. It is clearly seen that it can be approximated with several linear segments which indicate the presence of thermally activated processes resulting in the changes of C_S . Obtained values of activation energies and corresponding temperature ranges are presented in Table 3. Similar dependences are obtained for other samples.

Figure 6. The temperature dependences of $\ln(\chi_{EPR} T)$ on $1/T$ for the sample **3**. The linear dependences allow use of Arrhenius equation to determine activation energies of processes responsible for the decrease in the spin concentration.

Table 3. The activation energies of thermal processes responsible for changes in spin concentration of the studied samples. The temperature range of these processes is indicated in brackets.

sample 1		sample 2		sample 3
Fresh [K]	Stored [K]	Fresh [K]	Stored [K]	
924 (300-270 K)	295 (292-265 K)	197 (294-270)	145 (290-200 K)	117 (295-165 K)
11.3 (30-4.2 K)	43 (150-60 K)	106 (260-190 K)	72 (160-120 K)	28 (120-70 K)
7 (90-30 K)	1.8 (40-4.4 K)	78 (170-90 K)	16 (100-50 K)	4.4 (50-20 K)
		15 (40-20 K)	2.3 (25- 4 K)	2.5 (15-4 K)
		2.2 (15-4.4 K)		

Interpretation of the temperature-dependent C_S requires discussion of the nature of PCs which can exist in GLC600. These centers are usually referred to as dangling bonds [43,44]. It is expected that plenty of dangling bonds are produced in the process of pyrolysis [7]. Their role was recently investigated by simulation of evolution of nanostructures and functional groups in glassy carbon under pyrolysis [45]. It was shown that such dangling bonds exist

predominately on the edges of flat components of GLC and to a lesser extent on edges of vacancy defects [45]. The term dangling bond is a general term referring to the unsaturated valence of an atom. However, the discovery of graphene gave impetus to experimental [46–50] and theoretical [47,51,52] studies of structural defects of this material. Since GLC is classified as graphene-related material with predominant sp^2 hybridization [5], we can expect similar defects in it. Published studies show that only a small fraction of such defects exhibit a magnetic moment. The single carbon vacancies [46,47,53,54] are considered in modeling the structure of GLC600 (Figure 1). The edge states on zigzag edges [55,56] are met frequently in various graphene fragments, therefore they are present in all GLCs. The grain boundaries [57,58] arising in the polycrystalline graphene due to deviation from bipartite characteristics of the pristine graphene are probable in GLC600. There are also surface defects resulting from covalent attachment of carbon [59] or foreign adatoms or molecules to a graphene layer [60]. Additionally, the interlayer carbon atoms or aromatic rings considered in structural models discussed above form covalent bonds with graphene layers and can induce the appearance of magnetic moments delocalized on the neighboring atoms. The unpaired spins can also appear due to charge carriers, electrons and holes, in the sp^2 hybridized carbon materials. A thermal excitation of an electron into the antibonding orbital produces two magnetic moments. One can expect that the graphene fragment built of several rings is sufficient for such excitations. In disordered graphene-related materials such as GLC600, charge carriers are localized on these fragments, but can move within them. To distinguish such charge carriers from conduction electrons, we will use the term itinerant. While there is no DC conductivity in our material, these itinerant magnetic moments of holes and electrons contribute to χ_{EPR} .

Despite a large variety of possible PCs, the observed EPR spectrum is a single Lorentzian line and the $\pi/2$ pulse produces a monoexponential FID. This means that either one type of PC strongly dominates the other contributions, or exchange interactions between the centers average the more complex EPR spectrum to a single line. The high C_S values suggest the presence of dipolar interactions, which should result in a line broadening and its Gaussian shape. Since the Lorentzian lineshape is observed in the whole temperature range, the exchange interactions dominates. In disordered and nonconducting GLC600, with a spin concentration suggesting one unpaired electron per 500 carbon atoms, long-range magnetic order is not expected. Therefore, in the absence of antiferromagnetic order, the $C_S(T)$ dependences can be explained by the disintegration of exchange-coupled pairs of unpaired electrons with increasing temperature. Depending on the location of PCs, these pairs can exist either in a triplet ground state with $S = 1$ (the same sublattice) or in a singlet one with $S = 0$ (for different graphene

sublattices). The disintegration of pairs in the singlet ground state increases the number of PCs in the doublet state and magnetic susceptibility. For triplet ground states, the situation is more complex. There is no evidence for the presence of triplet states in GLC600, because the Rabi oscillation frequency is the same as for the reference with electron spin $S = 1/2$. However, pairs with the triplet ground state cannot be excluded. When the fine splitting (FS) is large, only a small fraction of all PCs in the triplet state can be excited by the MW pulse simultaneously with the doublet states. Since values of ΔE_{ST} depends on the shape and size of the graphene fragments [61], one should expect dispersion of these values, leading to blurring of the EPR spectra of triplets in a wide range of magnetic fields. As a result, only a small fraction of all triplet-state PCs contributes to the observable signal and triplet states are practically undetectable in EPR.

Disintegration of the exchange-coupled pairs requires some disturber, and its origin can be deduced from the fact that the highest concentration of PCs is observed for the least degassed fresh samples **1** and **2**. Perturbations to the exchange interactions can be generated by residual molecular oxygen adsorbed in these samples, which shortens the spin relaxation time T_2 and results in a loss of phase coherence of PCs. The O_2 molecule in the triplet ground state can also produce geometrical frustration acting as a third partner in the exchange-coupled cluster which can lead to the ground state with $S = 1/2$ [62]. Such situations are considered theoretically for ideal, Kagome-like arrangement of magnetic moments. However, in real materials the disturbance introduced by the third magnetic moment can be temperature-dependent. At high temperatures, when thermal excitations already disturb the mutual orientation of the interacting magnetic moments, third magnetic moment in the position close to the form of an equilateral triangle can cause significant disruptions. It can be an O_2 molecule or any third PC in the appropriate position to disrupt the interaction of the exchange-coupled pair.

Small and defected graphene-like planes, which are postulated as the basic graphene-like building blocks of GLC600, contain fragments built of hexagons and resemble open shell structures, exhibiting a biradical character [61]. The ΔE_{ST} values calculated and observed for pairs of PCs localized in such structures are in most cases too high to allow population of the excited state at temperatures below 300 K [61]. Therefore, the increase in C_S can be explained by the increase in the number of PCs in doublet states ($S = 1/2$) caused by disintegration of pairs with high ΔE_{ST} regardless of their ground state and can explain the $C_S(T)$ dependence observed for GLC600. For such a scenario, the ΔE values obtained from the dependences of

$\ln(\chi_{EPR}T)$ vs $1/T$ (Figure 6 and Table 3) are significantly lower than the expected ΔE_{ST} and should be treated as energies of pair disintegration/reconstruction.

5. Conclusions

We have studied the structure and magnetic properties of glass-like carbon pyrolyzed at 600 °C. Unusual non-Curie temperature dependences of paramagnetic susceptibility, measured by continuous wave EPR in the range of 4-300 K, were observed for differently degassed samples. The strong influence of sample preparation conditions (degassing, annealing and storage time) on these dependences was explained by nanoporosity detected by SAXS technique. Because GLC600 samples are not electrically conductive, their $\chi_{EPR}(T)$ dependences cannot be explained by the contribution of Pauli paramagnetism. They have been associated with temperature-induced changes in concentration of PCs caused by the disintegration of their exchange-coupled pairs. These pairs can exist either in a triplet ground state or in a singlet one. However, the expected triplet states have not been detected in either continuous wave or nutation EPR experiments, perhaps due to the large fine splitting. It was shown that adsorbed gases cause the disintegration of exchange-coupled pairs, which is manifested in the strong $C_s(T)$ dependence. In order to better understand the nature of PCs and the mechanisms of their exchange coupling, the pulsed EPR studies of electron spin relaxation times and Rabi oscillations below 80 K are planned. The revealed temperature peculiarities of paramagnetism can be observed in other disordered carbon materials and our results will be helpful for their studying by EPR spectroscopy.

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